

Measuring the Relationship Between Immigration and Academics : Combatting Academic Disparities

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Abstract:

This paper explores the relationship between generational status and academic achievement amongst Asian American students. Asian American students are well documented as the most academically successful racial group in the US. This steep academic success is often attributed to the socio-cultural factors accompanied by immigrant status. When analyzing how this status affects Asian American students' academic achievement, it is important to observe how these socio-cultural factors can affect different generations. A mixed method approach was implemented with a correlational analysis and thematic analysis. A quantitative analysis was conducted through the use of a self-administered questionnaire. Academic achievement was quantified through students' GPA, which was then restandardized. Pearson's correlation coefficient was then utilized to calculate the correlation between GPA and generational status. To account for confounding variables, the two most prominent confounding variables in the field of academic achievement, mental health and family income, were selected and implemented into the survey, so correlations could be found between these factors and generational status as well. No correlation was found between generational status and family income or generational status and mental health, whereas a weak negative correlation was found between generational status and academic GPA. A thematic analysis of the qualitative data from the questionnaire revealed consistent themes of culture and parental figures encouraging better academic achievement whilst causing declines in mental health throughout all generations. Analyzing both data, it can be concluded that the difference in academic effects between different generations is miniscule regardless of differences in mental health or family income.

Keywords: *Immigration, academic achievement, Asian American, correlational analysis, thematic analysis, Asian American youth,*

1. Introduction

In this day and age, two main paths are credited towards success: generational success and education. However, the former path is only accessible for the more fortunate individuals in society. With education being a way for even common folk to attain a prosperous future, it is important that disparities in academic achievement between different groups are analyzed and reported, so institutions and families are better able to help their children prosper in this system. Without analyzing aforementioned disparities, education can quickly become a path towards success that only benefits a select few individuals, just like the other paths towards success.

Despite these concerns, there is a growing divide in educational achievement, specifically between higher income and lower income individuals. In recent years, the gap in academic achievement has been pronounced by the Scholastic Aptitude Test, or the SAT. As shown through the 2022 annual SAT report, higher income was shown to positively correlate with higher SAT scores (Collegeboard, 2022). This environment dictated by financial status may lead to a feeling of hopelessness amongst lower income households. However, students very much may be able to succeed whilst not descending from higher income households. In a 2014 study, Hsin and Xie found that Asian Americans typically achieve greater academic success than their White American counterparts, not as a result of financial status but due to greater academic effort (Hsin & Xie, 2014). These larger amounts of effort stemmed from status as an immigrant and cultural values. Because generational status was deemed a large determinant for greater academic success, this research paper aims to find the correlation between immigrant status and academic achievement amongst Asian American students. Using a correlational analysis, data will be collected from Asian students regarding both academic achievement and personal motivators to establish any possible correlations, finding any prominent correlations

can provide information on whether individuals of non-immigrant status and motivations stemming from other areas can achieve academic success through greater academic effort, just as the Asian immigrant students of America. Parents and academic institutions can employ this data to combat any present disparities in academic achievement seen in students. To provide said data, this paper will strive to answer the following: “How does generational status affect academic status among Asian American students?”

1.1 The Importance of Motivation in Regards to Academic Success

When discussing generational status, it is important to note that this refers to the place of birth regarding a person or person’s parents. For example, an individual born outside of the U.S. would be considered first-generation, whereas someone whose parents were born outside of the US would be considered second-generation. Third Generation individuals are people who themselves and their parents were born in the U.S.

When discussing matters of Asian academic success, the majority of the studies done on the matter do focus on academic motivation as opposed to academic success. Thus, it’s important to establish the relationship between these two factors. In a 2019 paper, academic achievement is identified as an “an important determinant of academic success” (Steinmayr et al, 2019). Steinmayr and her colleagues employed a correlational analysis to find the relationship between academic motivation in different subjects and those students’ performance on said subjects. Closely similar correlation coefficients were found between all subjects assessed that showed a positive correlation between academic motivation and academic achievement. Although this data was taken from German students, it can be assumed these findings can be applied universally, as subjects such as mathematics were also tested. Through these findings, it

can be concluded that higher academic achievement can lead to an overall greater level of academic accomplishment.

Additionally, it's also imperative to analyze the repercussions that come with lower levels of academic achievement. A study performed by a Florida State University Psychology professor and a group of fellow professors from the University of Jyväskylä found a positive correlation between lower levels of academic motivation and poorer levels of academic performance and ability to form bonds with peers (Laursen et al, 2022).. These poor levels of achievement and peer-acceptance would quickly grow, leading to students finding difficulty in establishing productive work schedules and interacting with peers in later years. It is important to note, however, that this study consisted of a longitudinal study with a sample group that consisted of first grade students at the start of the study and fourth grade students at the end. Older students may not experience the same snowball effect if they have experience with effective work schedules in the past. Additionally, this study was conducted in Finland, so the social response that poorly motivated students received may be different from the social response poorly motivated students might face. As a result, the study conducted in this paper will strive to include all age groups. Nonetheless, the positive correlation between poor academic motivation and poor academic performance is irrefutable, and the aforementioned contingencies are still possible to take place.

These studies show a trend marking the importance of academic motivation and its effects on academic performance. This calls into question the origin of academic motivation amongst Asian American students, as these differing origins may offer different levels of academic motivation.

1.2 Motivation Amongst Generations

As established, academic motivation is a large factor in regards to academic achievement. This correlation may contribute towards much of the academic success seen amongst Asian American immigrant students. It's also imperative to understand where this motivation stems from to understand why academic motivation is so high amongst Asian American immigrant students.

Sociology professors Lanuza and Felciano's (2015) paper employs a regression analysis to examine why children of immigrants exhibit higher levels of academic motivation (Lanuza & Felciano, 2015). The researchers primarily used data from Early Childhood Longitudinal Study while using the National Longitudinal Study for a bit. As the data from these longitudinal studies contained personal student experiences, regression models showed that the higher levels of academic motivation amongst children of immigrants came from higher levels of parental expectations, greater interest in school, and foreign language proficiency since childhood. Although the general focus of this study is early childhood, these findings support the notion of first and second generation Asian American students holding more academic motivation than later generations due to generation status. Because generational status is a constant, it can be assumed that these can be shown to affect Asian American students outside of just early childhood.

Whilst Lanuza and Feliciano's study reports a higher level of academic motivation amongst first and second generation Asian American students, a 2019 study investigates a distinction between the two generations (Moon and Ruiz-Casares, 2019). This paper focuses on the excess pressure that comes with the high expectations that come from Asian immigrant parents. Also, a great deal of stress is placed on the immigration

process that immigrant parents had faced and how that now affects their decision, ensuring that the distress analyzed in the study is a result of immigrant status. Amongst first and second generation Asian students, second generation Asian students fixated on the high parental standards as a means to succeed, and first generation Asian students used their awareness of their parents' difficulties as means of internal motivation. Additionally, first generation Asian students showed much higher depression scores. This paper revealed the difference in motivations seen in first and second generation Asian students, and at the same time, it introduced topics like mental health, which may hinder the positive effects brought by academic motivation. It should be considered, however, that this study took place in Canada, and the immigration process in the U.S. is known to be much more challenging, so the data may be more extreme, but it should still relatively share the same pattern, as it would be natural for first generation children to be more aware of their parents' hardships, as they faced these hardships with their parents.

1.3 Gap and Hypothesis

Although many of the sources detail generational status to be a positive variable affecting academic achievement amongst Asian students, the topic of differences in generational status affecting academic achievement in different manners is not mentioned. Additionally, Asian American students are reported to be most academically successful (Harvard Graduate School of Education, 2017). Thus, it is important to research the effects of generational status on academic achievement among Asian American students in recent years. Understanding this gap is imperative, as doing so can provide more knowledge on the matter of how students can use academic motivation as means to academic success, which may allow institutions to combat

disparities in academic achievement. This gap will be approached by researching in the age range of 10 - 25 years. This can first affirm whether or not Lanuza and Felicinao's findings can be extended outside of young childhood and secondly whether generational status and academic stay correlated amongst numerous age groups. It can be hypothesized that first and second generation students will perform better academically than third generation students due to an agreement of sources that immigrant status correlates with higher academic motivation. Lastly, second generation Asian students can be expected to perform better academically than first generation Asian students due to lower depression scores and similar regard in terms of academic motivation amongst sources

2. Methodology

The present study aims to fully analyze the relationship between generational status and the academic performance of Asian American students to better inform educational institutions on possible initiatives to better student communities. Thus, a mixed methods approach was used, meaning data was collected and analyzed in both a quantitative and qualitative manner. The tool used to do so was a digital self-administered survey questionnaire. This type of survey questionnaire allowed for a greater outreach, allowing more diverse opinions and perspectives. With more perspectives, this research paper will be able to pinpoint a more accurate relationship within the data gap of generational and academics amongst Asian American students. Quantitatively, A correlational analysis was carried out, utilizing the patient health questionnaire anxiety and depression scale (PHQ-ADS) while at the same asking questions regarding the student's academic achievements as well as demographic questions in the survey. The survey questionnaire also asked participants to answer a number of prompts. The qualitative aspect of the survey questionnaire served to counteract a common fault in the correlational analysis: the inability to establish cause and effect relationships.

As mentioned previously, the survey was self-administered online, so there were no restrictions regarding area of residency, as long as the participant resided within America and was Asian American. Participants Data were gathered through a number of online social media platforms, such as Discord, Reddit, and Instagram. Respondents were briefly informed on the purpose of this study to gain truthful and reliable information. Additionally, respondents were ensured complete anonymity and confidentiality to prevent any discomfort.

2.1 Materials

When analyzing academics, mental health is an important factor, if not one of the most. In fact, both anxiety and depression are shown to interfere with working memory, leading to a decrease in academic success (Mathew Owens et. al, 2012). Thus, the PHQ-ADS scale was used, a combination of the PHQ-9 (patient health questionnaire) and GAD-7 (general anxiety disorder) scales, the most applicable in the survey questionnaire, as not only does the PHQ-ADS have a Cronbach's Alpha (internal consistency score) of .8 to .9 (Kroenke et.al, 2017). Apart from the reliability of the PHQ-ADS scale, it serves its purpose well, as it can assess both anxiety and depression, two different but similarly contributing factors to academic success.

2.2 Data Collection by Means of the PHQ-ADS Scale

This scale consists of 18 prompts with 16 employing a likert scale type answer choice from a range 0-3 and two multiple choice questions. The value 0 was associated with "Not At All" whereas, 3 was associated with "Nearly everyday", and the two multiple choice questions have 4 answer choices consisting of "not difficult at all", "somewhat difficult", "very difficult", and "extremely difficult". Before completing this portion of the survey questionnaire, participants were asked to detail their relationships with their parents in regards to academics and how that may have affected their mental health.

For the analysis of the scale, all the values in likert scale type questions were added to find a score with a domain of 0 and 48, where higher scores indicate more severe levels of depression and anxiety. Additionally, the prompts were then split up amongst questions in the PHQ-9 scale and questions in the GAD-7 scale to calculate individual depression and anxiety severity scores. The calculation process for the PHQ-9 scale and the GAD-7 scale were identical to the PHQ-ADS scale, where the values from the prompts were all added together for a final score, and the greatness of the final score indicated the severity of the disorder. The score from the PHQ-9 scale will fall between 0 and 28, while the score on the GAD-7 scale will fall between 0 to 21.

This data will serve the purpose of identifying the correlation between generational status and mental health which may assist in establishing causation relationships between generational

status and academic achievement among Asian American Students. To find the relationship between generational status, Pearson’s r will be utilized. As such, the covariance will be calculated in relation to the PHQ-ADS scale and generational status, using the following equation: $Covariance = \frac{\sum (PA_i - PA)(y_i - \bar{y})}{N - 1}$. After finding the covariance, it will be divided by the product of the two variable’s standard deviations to find the correlation coefficient.

The following chart details the variables within the covariance equation.

Table 1

Variable Definitions for the PHQ-ADS scale

Variable	Definition
PA _i	Data value of PHQ-ADS scale
PA	Mean value of PHQ-ADS scale

Notes. PHQ-ADS = Patient Health Questionnaire Anxiety and Depression Scale.

Table 2

Variable Definitions for Generational Status

Variable	Definition
y _i	Data value for generational status
y	Mean value for generational status
N	Number of data values

2.3 Quantitatively Examining the Participant’s Identity

Within the survey, participants were also asked to detail their grade point averages (GPA), while also discussing whether or not they were a first, second, or third- generation Asian American student. Participants were also asked for information regarding their family’s household income if they lived with their parents, and their personal income if the participant lived. This was because of the fact that low family income is associated with low academic performance (Morissey et. al, 2013). Thus, it’s important to find the correlation between

financial income and generational status among Asian Americans to establish any relationships that may be contributing to the relationship between generational status and academic achievement. Additionally, a quantitative analysis will be conducted to examine the relationship between GPA and generational status. When calculating their academic performance, only participants' GPAs were used due to the unstandardized nature's class rank and how different participants did not take part in the same standardized testing. However, to ensure the standardization of GPAs, many data inputs for participants' GPA had to be recalculated. Thus, all GPAs were recalculated to be in a 4.0 grade scale, and for highschool students who reported unweighted GPAS, they would receive an additional .1 to their GPA for every Advanced Placement (AP) course or International Baccalaureate (IB) course and an additional .05 to their GPA for every Honors and Dual-Enrollment class. For highschool participants that did not elaborate on what kind of advanced course they took part in, only providing the amount they did, it will be assumed they took part in AP courses, as those are most abundant compared to the other advanced course types. This is because Honors classes are generally less difficult compared to AP and IB classes, and most Dual-Enrollment courses offered to highschool students are entry-level, which are also generally less difficult than AP and IB classes. As for undergraduate and graduate students with unweighted GPAs, their GPA would be calculated in relation to the rigor of their courses. Each honors course would warrant each participant to receive an additional .05, and each advanced course would warrant an additional .1 to be added to their gpas. Then, Pearson's correlation coefficient would be utilized here as well.

First, for the covariance between GPA and generational status, the following formula would be used: $Covariance = \frac{\sum (GPA_i - GPA)(y_i - y)}{N-1}$. Then, this would be divided by the product of the standard deviations of both variables for the correlation coefficient.

As for the correlational analysis between financial income and generational status, Pearson's correlation coefficient will be used once again. Furthermore, for certain participants that chose to give a range for their income, the median of the provided range will be used for their data input. To find the covariance between financial income and generational status, the following formula will be used: $Covariance = \frac{\sum (F_i - F)(y_i - y)}{N-1}$. Afterwhich, for the correlation coefficient, the covariance will be divided by the product of the standard deviation of financial income and generational status.

Table 3

Variable Definitions for GPA

Variable	Definition
GPA _i	Data value for GPA
GPA	Mean value for GPA
F _i	Data value for financial income
F	Mean value for financial income

2.4 Qualitative Data via Questionnaire Prompts

When gathering qualitative data, the best way was definitely the survey questionnaire. With the complete anonymity that the survey questionnaire provides, participants would feel less threatened when answering the prompts in the questionnaire. To add on, the survey questionnaire allowed for additional information to make sense of the quantitative data. As discussed in the literature review, parental and cultural factors were found to be extremely influential in children’s academic achievement and mental health. Thus, in an attempt to further understand the relationship between generational status and academic achievement amongst, prompts were administered regarding these topics. The prompts were as follows:

Table 4

Survey Questions on Parental and Cultural Influence

Questions
How have your parents affected your outlook and motivation regarding academics?
How have your parents affected your mental health?
How do you feel your own culture has affected your academics?
How has your mental health been affected as a result of your culture?

After the data collection period was finished, all the responses to the survey questionnaire were saved on google sheets due to the facilitated connection between google forms and google sheets. There were no names recorded in the sheets, as the survey did not record any names or emails to eliminate potential bias and ensure complete anonymity.

When analyzing the questionnaire responses, The questionnaire was analyzed multiple times. Notably, following findings seen in past literature, themes were noted in these responses, especially those that allude to participants' parents and culture warranting said participant to feel more inclined to perform well academically, while also negatively affecting participant's mental health. For the prompts regarding academics, underlying themes of participants' dissatisfaction were considered. The thematic analysis was utilized here as a result of its ability to decipher underlying themes regarding the relationship between academic achievement among Asian American students and generational status.

The quantitative data gathered was analyzed through the aforementioned regression model in a google spreadsheet. The spread sheet consisted of the participants' grade, gpa, PHQ-ADS scores, and generational status. Data were organized in stratas in relation year in highschool/middle school/college in case the relationship differed amongst age groups as a result of the participant's current relationship with their parents as well as to see how this relationship conflicted with self-efficiency. Then, the regression analyses were carried out with the use of google l sheets. Finally, the data was organized in sharts including other statistical measures including standard deviation and covariance. After recording all this data on the google sheet, it was used in tandem with the data from the thematic analysis to synthesize any plausible conclusions.

2.5 Consent and Ethical Considerations

All ethical considerations were followed for this study. Informed consent was taken from all participants for data collection through a consent form within the survey/questionnaire. No identifiers such as names or pictures were disclosed in the article or while conducting the study. Ethical guidelines of research were followed, ensuring that participants were fully informed about the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without any consequences. Participants were also assured that their responses would be anonymized and used solely for research purposes.

3. Results

All the findings below were gathered through both qualitative and quantitative means. For the quantitative analysis, regression models were utilized, and no significant correlations were found between generational status and academic performance, financial income, or mental health. With the use of the formula presented in the methodology, the calculations for this research were done manually. Due to the ordinal nature of generational status, numbers ranging from 1 to 3 were assigned to the generational statuses when calculating the correlation coefficient. First generation Asian American students were assigned the value 1, whereas second generation and third generation (and later) were assigned 2 and 3, respectively. After graphing the data through google sheets, a linear regression was performed to better showcase the data in relation to a line of best fit. The trendline is shown in black and is accompanied by the $y=mx+b$ formula. The correlation coefficient is not shown from the linear regression model, as the correlation coefficient will be shown through pearson’s correlation model.

When analyzing the qualitative data, all 4 themes presented in the methodology section were found in abundance within the survey questionnaire responses. The themes identified and their frequency were organized in the chart below:

Table 5

Themes Related to Parental and Cultural Influences on Academics and Mental Health

Theme	Definition	Number of Interviews Present
Parents and Academics	Participants are pushed in regards to academics due to their parents	36
Parents and Mental Health	Participants’ mental health has negatively affected as a result of their parents	30
Culture and Academics	Participants are pushed to achieve greater in terms of academics because of their culture	25

<p>Culture and Mental Health</p>	<p>Culture has resulted in negative effects to participants' mental health</p>	<p>25</p>
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Figure 1.1

Regression Scatterplot of GPA and Generational Status

Figure 1.2

Regression Scatterplot of Annual Family Income and Generational Status

Figure 1.3

Regression Scatterplot of PHQ-ADS Scores and Generational Status

PQH-ADS Scores vs. Generational Status

Table 6

Descriptive Statistics for GPA and Generational Status

Definition	Value
Mean value for GPA	3.771
Sample Standard Deviation for GPA	3.765
Mean value for Generational Status	1.415
Sample Standard Deviation for Generational Status	13.951
Number of Data Values	41

Table 7

Correlation Analysis Between GPA and Generational Status

Statistic	Value
Covariance	-1.502

Correlation Coefficient	-0.2073
<i>p</i> -Value	.19343

Table 8

Descriptive Statistics for Annual Family Income and Generational Status

Definition	Value
Mean Value for Annual Family Income	87
Sample Standard Deviation for Annual Family Income	262,510
Mean Value for Generational Status	1.415
Sample Standard Deviation for Generational Status	13.951
Number of Data Values	41

Table 9

Correlation Analysis Between Annual Family Income and Generational Status

Statistic	Value
Covariance	105
Correlation Coefficient	0.0563
<i>p</i> -Value	.72662

Table 10

Descriptive Statistics for PHQ-ADS Score and Generational Status

Definition	Value
Mean Value for PHQ-ADS Score	25.341
Sample Standard Deviation for PHQ-ADS Score	5,925.22
Mean Value for Generational Status	1.415
Sample Standard Deviation for Generational Status	13.951
Number of Data Values	41

Table 11

Correlation Analysis Between PHQ-ADS Score and Generational Status

Statistic	Value
Covariance	-23.805
Correlation Coefficient	-0.0828
<i>p</i> -Value	.619043

Table 12

Probability Statistics

Stat.	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean
Mea sure	Annual Income First Gen.	Annual Income Sec. Gen.	Annual Income Third Gen.	GPA First Gen.	GPA Sec. Gen.	GPA Sec. Gen.	PHQ ADS Score First Gen.	PHQ ADS Score Sec. Gen.	PHQ ADS Score Third Gen.

Value	100,420	81,210	70,000	3.81	3.65	3.55	24.4	27	14
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All the graphs and charts above represent all 41 participants in the survey-questionnaire. The scatter plot was formed as all variables within the study were ordinal, meaning all values were ranked in natural order, so a graph, which represents equally spaced units, is the perfect representation. As shown through the charts, the correlation coefficient between GPA and generational status was -0.2073. Although a negative correlation, the relationship between the variables is very weak. Additionally, the correlation coefficients for generational status and annual family income and PHQ-ADS scores are 0.0563 and -0.0828, respectively. These correlation coefficients are extremely low, practically 0, showing no correlation. Despite the lack of strong correlations, significant conclusions can be drawn. While the correlation coefficient between GPA and generational status is weak, it is not weak enough to be discarded, giving its negative correlation some merit. This suggests that as generational status increases, GPA is more likely to decrease. The data supports this, showing each generation's mean GPA getting lower as generational status increases. However, this finding is not definitive and does not outweigh the low correlation coefficient. Another notable finding is that academic performance remained relatively high among all generations, in spite of the negative correlation. This supports previous findings that conclude Asian American students perform well academically. Lastly, the p-value regarding this correlation also supports this idea, as it is close to being somewhat statistically significant: 0.19343. A p-value of 0.19343 suggests an approximate 80% likelihood of this finding having a relationship. When looking at the correlations regarding generational status and annual family income and PHQ-ADS score, however, it can be concluded that there is no relationship present between annual family income or PHQ-ADS score and generational status. Not only were the correlation coefficients between these variables extremely close to 0, these relationships yield high p-values, .72662 and .619043, respectively. This suggests that there is a 72.7% likelihood that there is no relationship between annual family income and generational status, while there is a 61.9% likelihood that there is no relationship between generational status and PHQ-ADS score. However, when analyzing the mean annual family income between generations and mean gpa between generations, it can be observed that when one decreases, the other follows. Previous studies concluding a positive correlation between annual family income and academic performance support this finding. It's also alarming how both first and second

generation Asian American students on average yielded PHQ-ADS scores of 24.4 and 27, respectively. This coincides with the frequent theme of Asian parents and culture negatively affecting mental health observed in the questionnaire prompts

The survey-questionnaire prompts also provided notable data. All 4 frequent themes observed among participants suggested academic excellence was taken into heavy consideration and positively affected both parental and cultural factors, whereas mental health was often not taken into consideration and negatively affected. Another notable sub-theme found was that Asian culture was found to be extremely competitive, pitting Asian American students to pit against one another, resulting in both negative mental health and positive academics. Particularly, a specific participant wrote, “My own culture is all about being better in your school, so I feel like a failure”.

4. Discussion

The findings of this study form an important discussion. The results were gathered in hopes to answer the following question: “How does generational status correlate with academic success amongst Asian American students?” Contrary to the hypothesis, which suggested no correlation and that second generation Asian American students would perform the best overall, first generation Asian American students were found to be the best performing, and although weak, a negative correlation was found between GPA and generational status. Also, to further analyze the relationship between academic performance and generational status, certain confounding variables were selected to be analyzed: these being annual family income and mental health, which was quantitatively found through the PHQ-ADS test. However, all findings suggested a relationship existing between generational and annual family income or mental health. It was found, however, that mental health, on average, at an alarming rate among both first and second generation Asian American students. With high average scores of 24.4 out of 48 and 24.7 out of 48, it’s clear that mental health is in a poor state now amongst first and second generation Asian American students. With 5.9% of the total kindergarten to twelfth grade student population having Asian descent (NCES, n.d.), Asian students serve a significant minority in the school system, and these findings help understand cultural effects Asian students may experience in the classroom.

In terms of the qualitative responses, themes of both poor mental health and successful

academics emerged. Participants often reported that they received direct pressure from their parents and thus felt a need to perform well academically. A less noticeable theme was that of great filial piety. This select group of participants acknowledged the cultural and parental pressure they received in regards to academic achievement, but this did not result in poor mental health. These findings both coincide and conflict with conclusions from Jeongyoon Moon and Mónica Ruiz-Casares's findings. Moon and Monica find that first and second generation Asian students' awareness of their parents' difficulty is highly correlated with higher parental respect and acknowledgement of high parental expectations. Some of the responses that show filial piety and acknowledgement also mention awareness of their parent's intentions, but difficulty is not involved. It may, however, be a possible reason as to why this exists. However, where this paper's findings conflict with Moon and Monica's findings is in regards to motivators amongst first and second generation Asian students. In their study, second generation students were mostly found performing well academically due to parental pressure, whereas first generation students were found to have intrinsic motivation. In this study, however, both first and second generation were found to experience parental pressure and no mention of intrinsic motivation was made. Another discrepancy is the differences in mental health results between the two studies. In Moon's study, first generation Asian students were found with poorer mental health, whereas the opposite is observed in the study, although very slightly. This is most likely due to the slight differences in culture between the students in the two studies, as this study analyzed Asian American students, whereas Moon and Monica analyzed Asian Canadian students.

While adding to the extensive body of knowledge between Asian American students and their relationship with academics and mental health, a new body of knowledge has emerged. Previous studies, when analyzing Asian American academics, purely focused on comparing Asian American students to other groups and rarely discussed comparisons within Asian American groups. This study, on the other hand, focused purely on relationships between Asian American students. As a result, future research will be necessary to further understand this relationship between generational status and Asian American students. For future research, a self-administered questionnaire can be disregarded, as the self-administered nature of the questionnaire resulted in many inconclusive responses this time and may have warranted participants to remain untruthful. Furthermore, the non-statistically significant p-values found this time can be circumvented in future studies with a larger sample size. Further research is

important, as truly understanding relationships between Asian American students and how outside factors affect their academic performance can help combat any academic disparities.

5. Conclusion

This study strived to investigate the relationship between generational status and academic achievement among Asian American students. To further understand this relationship, confounding variables, specifically financial status and mental health, were also examined in relation to generational status. The findings indicated there was no correlation between generational status and financial status or mental health, with a high null hypothesis probability. For generational status and academic achievement among Asian American students a somewhat negative correlation was implied, but the statistical significance of the relationship was weak. Mental health was calculated in a quantitative manner for all 41 participants with the use of PHQ-ADS scale. Financial status and academic achievement were calculated using annual family income and GPAs, respectively. In the same survey questionnaire that collected this quantitative data, qualitative data was collected via short response prompts. Upon completion of the data collection, a thematic analysis was conducted on every response. The analysis revealed themes of academic achievement being pushed through culture and parental involvement, while both culture and parental involvement were found to be factors encouraging negative mental health as well.

When examining research regarding Asian American academics, a common theme of academic success is attributed. When examining reasons as to why, first/second generation status is often brought up as an important factor, citing the socio-cultural nature associated with first and second generation status amongst Asian Americans. However, generational status among Asian American students and academics has never been the sole focus of a study, leading to a lack of information regarding the idea. Thus, a lack of data was presented in regards to the difference between separate generations in Asian Americans. The only data available on the matter was regarding Asian Canadians from Ruiz-Casares and Moon, and instead of academic achievement, academic motivation and mental health were analyzed. A response to this gap would prove critical to better understanding academic relationships among Asian American students. This research was successful in better understanding the relationship between generational status and Asian American students, as no significant correlation was found. The

differences in data between this study and Moon's study further cement this study's necessity, as the data show future research regarding the same topic can notice the unreliability of citing data regarding Asian Canadian students in regards to Asian American. This study's mixed-method approach gives the findings merit, as both methodologies allow a better understanding of the other.

Despite this paper's academic merit, challenges presented themselves throughout the research process, limiting the applicability of the study. As previously mentioned, the study was fairly miniscule, amounting 41 participants, considering the sheer amount of Asian American students. This undeniably limits the statistical significance of the data. Future research on the matter should strive for a larger sample size to ensure more statistical significance. Additionally, all the participants consisted of either high school students or college students. This ultimately limits the paper's understanding of the relationship between generational status and academic achievement among Asian American students. As a result, the generalizability of this study is also limited. Furthermore, the self-administered nature of the data collection method led to many discrepancies among data. Certain responses remained unclear or too short to draw meaningful conclusions. This can be countered in future research with the use of an ethnography as opposed to a survey questionnaire when collecting qualitative data. This can allow for a natural analysis that can provide more consistent data.

In short, this study was able to add noteworthy information to the existing body of knowledge. Although all correlations found were weak, quantitative and qualitative observations yield notable findings in the suggestions of possible trends and patterns that both shed new information while reaffirming previous data. The themes of poor mental health support longstanding information discussing the cultural stigmas around mental health and available support systems in Asian American support systems (Nishi, 2012). This is reaffirmed by the high average PHQ-ADS scores displayed throughout both first and second generation Asian Americans. At the same time, both generations had relatively high levels of academic achievement. This does conflict with general knowledge regarding education. Generally, poorer mental health is associated with lower levels of academics (Owens et al., 2012). It should be noted, however, that the study recording this data conducted their study across many racial groups. Seeing how these findings do not coincide with the findings of this study, the non-homogenous nature of academics between racial groups is highlighted, warranting further

research. Hopefully, understanding of different educational patterns and advances between different racial groups expands, so the ability to promote adequate educational practices and combat academic disparities will ultimately improve this nation's academic institutions.

References

- College Board. (2022). *2022 New York SAT Suite of Assessments annual report*.
<https://reports.collegeboard.org/media/pdf/2022-new-york-sat-suite-of-assessments-annual-report.pdf>
- Feliciano, C., & Lanuza, Y. R. (2016). The Immigrant Advantage in Adolescent Educational Expectations. *The International Migration Review*, *50*(3), 758–792.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/43948671>
- Harvard Graduate School of Education. (2017). The other achievement gap.
<https://www.gse.harvard.edu/ideas/usable-knowledge/17/04/other-achievement-gap>
- Hsin, A., & Xie, Y. (2014). Explaining Asian Americans' academic advantage over Whites. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *111*(23), 8416–8421. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1406402111>
- Laursen, B., Richmond, K. A., Kiuru, N., Lerkkanen, M. K., & Poikkeus, A. M. (2022). Off on the wrong foot: Task avoidance at the outset of primary school anticipates academic difficulties and declining peer acceptance. *European Journal of Developmental Psychology*, *19*(4), 601–615. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17405629.2021.1936491>
- Moon, J., & Ruiz-Casares, M. (2019). Family's Migration Experience and Distress Among Asian-Canadian Immigrant Youth. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, *50*(1), 7–32.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/26740043>
- National Center for Education Statistics. (n.d.-a). *Enrollment and percentage distribution of enrollment in public elementary and secondary schools, by race/ethnicity and level of education: Fall 1999 through fall 2031*.
https://nces.ed.gov/programs/digest/d22/tables/dt22_203.60.asp
- Nishi, K. (2012, May 1). *Students' corner*. American Psychological Association. from
<https://www.apa.org/pi/oema/resources/ethnicity-health/asian-american/article-mental-health>
- Owens, M., Stevenson, J., Hadwin, J., & Norgate, R. (2012). Anxiety and depression in academic performance: An exploration of the mediating factors of worry and working memory. *School Psychology International*, *33*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034311427433>

Steinmayr, R., Weidinger, A. F., Schwinger, M., & Spinath, B. (2019). The importance of students' motivation for their academic achievement: Replicating and extending previous findings. *Frontiers in Psychology, 10*, 1730. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01730>